

seedling, and covered with a fine fiber glass-mesh cage. Damage was scored on the 0-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)* when TN1 was killed.

Population growth was studied by infesting 30-d-old potted test plants with five pairs of GLH adults. The plants were covered with mylar film cages and arranged in a randomized complete block design, replicated five times. Nymphs

Pest resistance— other pests

New ufra-resistant rice lines

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During 1990-93, we tested and selected 29 F₂ populations and their progenies for ufra (*Ditylenchus angustus*) resistance. One hundred twenty-four selected lines of F₃ populations were further evaluated in 1993. Seeds of each of these entries were sown in pots and inoculated with 100 nematodes/plant at 15 d. Entries were scored 6 wk after inoculation based on leaf symptoms of susceptibility (Fig. 1a) and resistance (Fig. 1b-d).

Ten seedlings from each of the entries with resistance symptoms were transplanted for field evaluation from booting to flowering stages. A few seedlings with primary infestations and resistance symptoms were marked with

and adults on each plant were counted 30 d after infestation.

Thirteen varieties, ASD7, Tendeng, Rhissa, Sefa, Badal, Chota Digha, Chiknal, Ptb8, ASD8, Tapl796, Moddai Karuppan, Choron Bawla, and Laki 659, were rated as resistant in the seedbox screening test (see table). Pankhari 203 with *Glh 1* gene, and Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 with a dominant gene, were rated as susceptible. Population

increase was significantly higher on TN1, Pankhari 203, Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 than that on the resistant varieties

Among the GLH resistance genes identified at IRRI, *Glh 1* and a dominant gene in Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 do not confer resistance to GLH populations in Tamil Nadu while varieties with *Glh 2*, *Glh 3*, *glh 4*, *Glh 5*, *Glh 6*, *Glh 7*, *Glh 1* + *Glh 2*, and *Glh 3* + *Glh 5* do confer resistance. ■

Rice entries with ufra resistance. BRRI, Bangladesh.

Plant type	Entries		
Tall	IR63142-J6-B-1	IR63142-J8-B-2	IR63155-J9-B-1
	IR63174-J1-B-3	IR63188-J8-B-1	IR63188-J8-B-7
	IR63225-J2-B-1	IR63225-J2-B-4	IR63225-J2-B-6
	IR63645-J3-B-8		
Short	IR63174-J1-B-2-3	IR63174-J1-B-3-2	IR63174-J1-B-3-1
	IR63174-J1-B-4-3	IR63174-J1-B-6-3	IR63174-J2-B-4-2
	IR63174-J3-B-1-2		

red cellophane tape to record their survival. After establishment, five plants from each of these entries were dissected to count nematode populations. Rayada 16-06-1 was the resistant check and Habiganj Aman II, the susceptible check.

Sixty-four of the lines survived and flowered successfully. Ten deepwater rice lines (see table) had mild or no resistance symptoms. Seven other resistant entries (see table) were short-stemmed and may be used as resistance sources for rainfed lowland and irrigated rices. These entries had either Bazail 65 or Rayada 16-06 as a resistant parent.

Seedlings with primary infestations and resistance symptoms did not survive to maturity in all of the marked lines, but 91-96% of the secondary tillers that emerged from them survived and flowered successfully. In contrast, neither seedlings with primary infestations nor

secondary tillers of susceptible varieties survived. Nematode numbers were 0-101/plant in resistant entries and 141-3280 in the susceptible ones. Rayada 16-06-1, however, did not have any symptoms or nematodes in this experiment. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement

Twelve new rice varieties released for Orissa State, India

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The Orissa State Subcommittee recommended the release of 12 new rice varieties, developed by OUAT, for commercial cultivation in the state. Badami (OR164-5), Nilagiri (OR163-104), Khandagiri (OR811-2), and Ghanteswari (OR377-85-6) are adapted to rainfed and irrigated upland ecosystems; Birupa (OR253-2), Meher (OR526-2008-4), Samanta (OR487-30-3) and Bhanja (OR443-80-4), four midseason varieties, are recommended for irrigated

Symptoms of ufra disease on rice leaves. Susceptible: splash pattern chlorosis (a); resistant: discrete or rounded chlorotic lesion (b, d), elongated chlorotic lesion (c).

Rice varieties recommended for release in Orissa State, India, during 1992-93.

Variety	Designation (IET no.)	Parentage	Major features	Maturity duration	Resistance	Av yield (t/ha)	Adaptability
Badami	OR164-5 (IET7259)	Suphala/Annapurna	Semidwarf, golden-colored hulls and kernels, medium-bold grains	90-95	Gall midge, leaf-folder, green leaf-hopper, bacterial leaf blight and blast	3.7	Rainfed and irrigated uplands
Nilagiri	OR163-104 (IET10393)	Suphala/DZ192	Semidwarf, straw-colored hulls, medium-bold grains, translucent white kernels	90-95	Bacterial leaf blight, blast, rice tungro virus, stem borer, leaf folder, gall midge 1	3.5	Rainfed and irrigated uplands
Khandagiri	OR811-2 (IET10396)	Parijat/IRI3429-94	Semidwarf, straw-colored hulls, medium-slender fine grains, translucent white kernels	90-95	Bacterial leaf blight, blast, sheath rot, gall midge, brown planthopper, white-backed planthopper	3.5	Rainfed and irrigated uplands
Ghanteswari	OR377-85-6 (IET9802)	IR2061-628/N22	Semidwarf, golden-colored hulls with medium-bold translucent dull red kernels	90-95	Bacterial leaf blight, blast, brown spot, gall midge, sheath blight, green leaf-hopper	3.5	Rainfed and irrigated uplands
Birupa	OR253-2 (IET8620)	Adt 27/IR8///Annapurna	Semidwarf, straw-colored hulls, medium-bold translucent white kernels	130-135	Bacterial leaf blight, blast, rice tungro virus, gall midge, stem borer, whorl maggot, leaf folder, and whitebacked planthopper	4.2	Irrigated and rainfed medium lands
Meher	ORS26-2008-4 (IET9849)	OBS677/IR2071//Vikram/W1263	Semidwarf, straw-colored hulls, medium-bold, translucent white kernels	135-140	Blast, bacterial leaf blight, sheath rot, brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, sheath blight, gall midge	4.4	Irrigated and rainfed medium lands
Samanta	OR487-30-3 (IET10451)	T90/IR8//Vikram///Siam29/Mahsuri	Semidwarf, straw-colored hulls, medium-bold translucent white kernels, dark green, erect flag leaves until maturity	135-140	Blast, bacterial leaf blight, sheath rot, gall midge 1, gall midge 4, white-backed planthopper, sheath blight	4.4	Irrigated and rainfed medium lands
Bhanja	OR443-80-4 (IET10738)	IR36//Hema Vikram	Semidwarf, straw-colored hulls, medium-bold grains, translucent white kernels, dark green erect flag leaves until maturity	140-145	Blast, bacterial leaf blight, sheath rot, gall midge 1, gall midge 4, sheath blight	4.0	Irrigated and rainfed medium lands
Mahalaxmi	OR621-6 (IET10048)	Pankaj/Mahsuri	Semidwarf, straw-colored hulls, medium-bold grains, translucent white kernels	150-155	Bacterial leaf blight, blast, false smut, leaf folder, green leafhopper	5.0	Lowlands
Manika	OR624-46 (IET9737)	CR1010/OBS677	Semidwarf, straw-colored hulls, medium-bold grains, dark green erect flag leaves, translucent white kernels	155-160	Bacterial leaf blight, blast, sheath rot, gall midge 1, gall midge 4, sheath blight, and brown planthopper	5.0	Lowlands
Urbashi	OR645-18 (IET10811)	Rajeswari/Jajati	Tall, straw-colored hulls, medium-bold grains, translucent white kernels	140-145	Blast, sheath blight, rice tungro virus, gall midge, leaf folder	4.8	Lowlands
Kanchan	OR609-15 (IET10016)	Jajati/Mahsuri	Tall, straw-colored hulls, medium-slender grains, translucent white kernels	150-155	Bacterial leaf blight, sheath rot, sheath blight, gall midge	4.5	Lowlands

ecosystems; and Mahalaxmi (OR621-6), Manika (OR624-46), Urbashi (OR645-18), and Kanchan (OR609-15) are suitable for lowland ecosystems.

The features of these varieties are listed in the table. ■